

Time, Architecture and Domination: The Valley of the Fallen

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El Valle de los Caídos – the Valley of the Fallen – is the largest fascist monument constructed during Franco's regime. It comprises the largest Civil War cemetery; the corpses of Franco and Primo de Rivera; the tallest Christian cross in the world; a basilica carved out in the mountain; a Benedictine monastery and a man-made forest with an area of more than 1 000 hectares. While the Valley's symbolic conflict in contemporary Spain has been studied extensively by anthropologists, sociologists, archaeologists and historians, there has been no comprehensive analysis of the monument's architecture and landscape, and the intentions of its creators during its inception.

This article shows how the spaces and every material object in the Valley of the Fallen was created to reinforce the narrative of the “new order”. The location, in the middle of the “royal route”, links Franco's rule to the history of the Spanish Empire. The structure, calculated to last more than 1000 years, comprises a timeless architecture able to outlive the regime. The carved basilica, filled with thousands of corpses, introduces eternal time to the monument. These elements are just some examples of how the promoters of the Valley of the Fallen used time as a design tool in the creation of a site that acts as a totalitarian micro-cosmos of the regime's ideology.

Current debates about the resignification of the Valley and other recent-past monuments could benefit from understanding how the design and the different temporal layers introduced during its creation play an active role in the monument's meaning over time. Ultimately, the project of the Valley of the Fallen shows how time could be used to create absolutist designs where their symbolic transformation needs to come together with a material one. Keywords: time; architecture; cultural landscape; memory; monument; history; fascism; Spain; power

1. Introduction: The conflict embedded in the architecture of the Valley.

November 20th, 1975: Francisco Franco dies in Spain. Three days later, his body is transported 60 km, from Madrid's Royal Palace to the Valley of the Fallen, where he is to be buried. The enormous architectonic compound was constructed under his

command with the primary aim of perpetuating the memory of the Civil War and thus preserving historic time in its materiality. The temporal narrative of the site tries not only to capture the war victory, but the whole history of Spain, as well. According to the architect of the monument, Franco intended for the monument not to be an inert archaeological site, but living architecture: “in it the pulse of the country had to beat with a depth and with a spiritual symbol superior to the memory of an episode, no matter how great its greatness” (Méndez 1982, 12). Time was planned to work for a period that was longer than the Civil War and to be able to commemorate and invoke the power of eternity. From the very beginning, time held the central role in the most iconic example of Francoist architecture and landscape, as stated in the official announcement of its construction:

“The dimension of our Crusade, the heroic sacrifices involved in the victory and the far-reaching significance that this epic episode has had for the future of Spain, cannot be perpetuated with the simple monuments often commemorated in towns and villages about the events of our history and the glorious deeds of her sons. The stones that are to be erected must have the grandeur of the ancient monuments, which defy time and oblivion.” (Decreto 1940).

Beginning at its origins, time and oblivion have been intrinsically embedded in the Valley of the Fallen to create a monument that was neither common nor a static piece of architecture and designed landscape. Spatially, it spans an area of more than 1 000 hectares in a valley called “Cuelgamuros,” using landscape and architecture to create a complex temporal experience. The Valley is the largest remaining example of fascist architecture and designed landscape in Europe. It is composed of an artificial forest; the world’s largest Christian cross; the biggest Civil War cemetery; a huge basilica carved from a stone hill; a Benedictine monastery; a guest house, and even an academic centre. Construction of the compound relied in part on forced labour (Sueiro 1976) and

financing through donations. During construction, more than 33 000 bodies of political prisoners were moved into the basilica from mass graves. Because of its spatial and conceptual features, the Valley of the Fallen occupies “an undefined space with blurred distinctions between a monument, a mass grave and an unacknowledged site of suffering for political prisoners during its construction” (Hepworth, 2014,464), building an architectonic compound around time; the temporality of the dead reinforces the religious intervention, which simultaneously merges with natural time in an idyllic landscape that attempts to construct the tempo of history and the legitimacy of Franco’s regime.

The radical use of time to build the Valley of the Fallen was meant to create a single memory of what happened, and the conflictive monument left in our present fills newspapers, TV shows, political debates and conversations in bars, where the debates range from calling for its total demolition to insisting on its total conservation.

Materiality has the potential to freeze meanings and establish unique narratives (Hodder 2012; Olsen 2010; Starzmann 2013) as intended by Franco, but this can only endure for a certain period of time.

The present situation of the Valley of the Fallen falls into the defined category of “memory wars” (Stockey 2013), which are nothing less than time battles about who has the right to invoke certain pasts and appropriate them by building material artefacts as irrefutable evidence. This conflict has even led to terrorist attacks on the monument: in 1962 by Defensa Interior Group; in 1999 by GRAPO, and in 2005 by ETA that confirm the importance of the Valley’s materiality in contemporary Spain. Originally designed to gather, collect, and represent the only memory of the war, or the Crusade, the Valley now also represents the conflict of the traces of violence, pain and torture during Franco’s regime: “A past that haunts like a phantom and therefore cannot be so easily

controlled or subject to a finite interpretation” (Domanska, 2005,405).

Although architecture plays a key role in the conflict of the Valley of the Fallen, the monument’s architecture and site design has been researched very little. There are examples of reflection about Francoist architecture (González-Capitel 1977; Sambricio 1977) and even analyses of buildings and monuments of Franco (López-Gómez 1995; Álvarez-Quintana 1997), but the presence of the Valley in those studies is testimonial. Despite the extensive literature about monumental architecture of the dictatorships in Italy and Germany (Marcello and Gwynne 2015; Gentile 2007; Golan 2009; Kallis 2014; Torisson 2010), in the case of the Valley, the most interesting studies have been developed by anthropologists, sociologists, ethnographers, or even archaeologists (Ferrándiz 2011; González-Ruibal 2014; Viejo-Rose 2011). Nonetheless, the architecture and landscape form the missing piece of a puzzle that cannot be totally grasped as yet. There is a particular lack in terms of the Valley’s function as a time collector and an aesthetical representation of a militarized and Catholic society. It has been consistently overlooked that Francisco Franco and the architects of the monument, Pedro Muguruza and Diego Méndez, designed the Valley of the Fallen to become an eternal metaphor of the regime’s ideology, aiming thereby to infuse the monument with a temporal dominance over Spanish history.

This article analyses how the Valley of the Fallen was produced, at the same time exposing time as the key element in the monument’s design. The goal of the article is to demonstrate that the intentions and tools used by the monument’s creators result in an artefact in which the relation between materiality and symbolism is unbreakable; therefore, for a resignification process to be considered, interventions must take both entities into account. To do that, the article uses legal and historic documents about the design of the Valley of the Fallen as a source, linking them with theoretical research

about monuments, memory, or history to understand its final materialization. Primarily, the research analyses the writings of architect Diego Méndez (1982) through his detailed descriptions in a book published in 1982, to establish a baseline of the intentions of the Valley's creators and expose the different temporal strategies used in the monument to construct an astonishingly complex time artefact.

The first part of the article debates theory about monuments, memory, and time concerning the Valley. The article then looks at the three most important spatio-temporal aspects of the architecture – the territorial, religious and material dimensions – to understand the different forms of time that are invoked in the monument. The last part of the article discusses the transversal relation of the whole monument and its elements – corpses, basilica, cross, landscape – to try to demonstrate that the Valley of the Fallen is a wholly temporal artefact designed to conquer the collective imaginary of both present and future. Ultimately, the article uncovers the complex tactics used by those in power to attempt to use architecture as a tool to dominate time, reinforce the status quo and construct a microcosmos of their ideological view. This adds an important variable to the debate on conflictive heritage sites, and especially to the Valley of the Fallen, and explains why the integrity of the monuments could not be an a priori assumption without the understanding the intentions of its creators and their material capacity to establish time narratives.

Figure 1. View of the entrance to the basilica at El Valle de los Caídos, Madrid, October 2018.

2. The temporal conflict of monuments

Some narratives can only be told intertwined with architecture, especially those of the powerful (Sudjic 2005); most of the time, these take the form of monuments. “Memory is bound up with power, and both memory, and its corollary, forgetting, are hegemonically produced and maintained” (Mitchell 2003,443). In this sense, the current discussion of the transformation of the Valley is a complex conflict in which the architecture plays a key role as mediator of a certain narrative and shows that materiality is not an inert quality of any building.

Although heritage is usually associated with positive value, critical thinking has lately begun to question this matter (Biran, Poria, and Oren, 2011; Logan & Reeves 2008; Macdonald 2009) and to look at monuments as a source of controversy (Winter 2010) in which their own subsistence is linked to their capacity to change meaning and resignification (Nora 1989; Viejo-Rose 2011). The narrative about the monument is always a temporal process in which context, time, materiality, and even economy (Harrison, 2013; Shepherd, 2013) are continuously reformulated. Still, the role of the material environment is diminished and sometimes seen as a passive element in the equation, or simply as a problematic operation (Koshar 2000). Commonly, debates about the resignification of conflictive monuments mostly deal with their contemporary symbolism, underestimating the importance of how the intentions of its creators shape materiality to prevent the integration of other narratives. This battle between present and past, in which the active role of the architecture and overall design becomes apparent, reveals the importance of understanding the origin of monuments to completely apprehend why its materiality is the point of departure in a conflict that has multiple sociological, political, cultural and even anthropological ramifications.

Architecture has been defined as “a conqueror of forgetfulness” (Ruskin 1902, 224), expressing the quality of certain buildings to become temporal artefacts and play an active role in the definition of collective memory. In this sense, the architectural typology of monuments “like remainders, are intrinsically temporal” (Neumann 2018, 334), and try to work with time as a fundamental part of their being (Stefanovic, Stig, and Viejo-Rose 1994; Sørensen 2015). In this case, the article demonstrates that the creators of the Valley of the Fallen were conscious in designing complex temporal strategies to imbue architecture with the regime’s sense of history in order to build a timeless experience for both past, present, and future visitors.

Especially interesting is the distinction that the architecture theorist Fredrik Torisson makes between the relic and the monument, in which the relic is a leftover of what happened, while the monument “is a time machine intended to remind us of a historical event or person as perceived by the monument’s creator” (Torisson 2010, 17). The monument is consciously designed to reach that goal and bring past memories into the present. It tries to capture the momentum of a certain memory and simultaneously freeze it, preserving the event in a built form (Deleuze 1994; Hutchings 2008) (Neumann 2018), encouraging “us to remember some things and to forget others” (Ladd 1997, 11). In this sense, the article carefully examines the words of the architect to track the importance he gives to design time as history and experience in the Valley of the Fallen through a series of artefacts that tell one single story: that of Franco’s regime. The article demonstrates how every element in the monument serves a function to construct the artificial memory of how those in power see the nation as a whole.

Memory, in this case, is a form of legitimization and a way of maintaining a certain regime (Foote, Tóth, and Árvay, 2000; Forest & Johnson, 2002; Lamp, 2011; Osborne, 1995; Till, 1999). Systems of memory, that is to say systems of temporality, are directly

targeted by the design of monuments, and thus introduce time as part of the architectural process. Those memories, those pasts and the conscious invocation of them, influence both spectators but also constructors (Favro, 1996); regardless of intensity, they are contained and preserved in physical landscapes (Halbwachs 1992; Koompong 2013), but not in a static way. The question, then, would be whether it is possible to change the memory of recent-past monuments without intervening in their materiality.

The long relation of history and memory (Le Goff 1992; Olick, Vinitzky-Seroussi, and Levy 2011; Hutton 2000) demonstrates that both concepts are dynamic and non-linear, and both depend on the spatial and temporal features of the present: “it is the timing component which gives structure to space and thus evokes the notion of place” (Parkes and Thrift, 1978, 119). To understand what architecture really does to construct a place, a message or a symbol, it is necessary to unify the two entities (Kärrholm 2015) and understand the material environment both in time and space simultaneously.

“Understanding the unity of timespace is to understand the unity of place” (Malpas 2015, 25), because in times of identity crisis, the narratives of memory and history are questioned through their architectural representatives (Forest and Johnson 2002) but their actual materialization and design are constantly overlooked.

Monuments, and especially the Valley of the Fallen, are one of the few architectural and landscape typologies in which time and its different heterochronic conceptions (Foucault 1986) are consciously included in the design and process of thinking of sites as a service in the forefront of ideological dominance. Monument sites undergo constant revision where the past and the now meld together for the apparition of new temporal narrative of both (Graham and Howard 2008) but its materiality is rarely and timidly intervened in. While the historic, political, ideological or artistic features of the Valley have been explored widely (Sueiro 2006; Calleja 2009; Aguilar-Fernández and

Humblebæk 2002; Olmeda 2009; Castro-Berrojo 2008; Solé-Barjau 2009), this has not been done from an architectural and material point of view that critically examines the process of the construction to understand what was intended to conquer and achieve by its creators. In this article, the process of designing the Valley of the Fallen is explored and discussed in depth to uncover the role of the monument's materiality in such a controversial work of design. Using original documents from the creators of the Valley of the Fallen, the article describes how deeply the ideology and the narrative of Franco's regime are embedded in the concrete and stones of the monument, thus proffering a missing piece to current debates about the edifice and demonstrating the need to investigate materiality when dealing with such architectonic pieces, if a complex understanding is meant to be achieved.

3. Territorial dimension: The use of time as history and nature

3.1. *The location as a link with history.*

Documentation of the Valley of the Fallen constantly references Franco's personal search to choose the location of the monument (Méndez 1982; Sueiro 1976). Beyond the rhetoric of the search, we do know that the choice was a thoughtful one, where "the election of the place has undoubtedly been a decisive contribution to what the Monument represents and has come to mean" (Méndez 1982,15).

The Valley of the Fallen is located only 10 km from the monastery "El Escorial", where the royal cemetery is located, in the so-called "royal route" that encompasses the royal palace, the palace of "La Granja", the palace of "Aranjuez", and its location served the purpose of connecting with the grandiose periods of Spanish history. In that sense, location, landscape and architecture were used to unite the time of Franco with the time of the empire "near El Escorial, with which it would be compared, making an easy –

and false – analogy of the two buildings and their eras both described as imperial splendor” (Llorente-Hernández 1995, 282).

The location choice sought to link the monument with the “royal route” of palaces in order to legitimize the regime as part of the history of Spanish kings (González-Ruibal 2009, 67). From a territorial point of view, by declaring the location of the Valley in between El Escorial and La Granja, Franco was positioning the crusade as part of the history of royalty. The location harks back to an ancient past that forms part of the present. In its architect’s words, the Valley of the Fallen was “nothing more and nothing less, than the altar of the Homeland, the altar of heroic Spain, mystical Spain and eternal Spain.” (Méndez 1982, 13). Therefore, the aim to reach eternal validity existed from the very beginning by trying to build an architecture able to surpass the episode of the war and write a new chapter in the Empire’s history. The boldness of this temporal link between the Valley and El Escorial was extensively explored by the architect, who even compared their respective economic values (Méndez 1982, 288).

The strategy of linking the ancient past to their present as a continuous entity was just one attempt to legitimize the regime through “invented traditions” (Hobsbawm 1983) that use aesthetic and material tools to directly relate the present with the past. For example, at the entrance to the Valley, there are four monoliths, called "Los Juanelos", which were sculpted during the reign of Carlos I and Felipe II. Again, the allusion to the temporality of the empire becomes evident through the use of architecture and landscape. Furthermore, the monoliths are claimed to be "sentinels of honor of the Valley of the Fallen" (Méndez 1982, 46), as they are the first visual element that the visitor encounters inside the gates. This strategy is not only a preserved memory, but also a material invocation to the historic narrative with which they want to unite the architectonic complex. Furthermore, the role of tourism and touristic pamphlets has

helped to strengthen this relation; “it helped to transfer consideration of the renaissance building as a historic landmark to the fascist monument” (Fuentes-Vega 2017, 84) by placing both buildings on the same touristic route and placing them adjacent to one another in catalogues, on posters and in diverse promotional material. In this sense, the National Patrimony Institution as the main producer of the monument’s tourist information, promoted the Valley of the Fallen as part of the Empire’s history without mentioning the recent violence of the Civil War and with an acritical understanding of the blood spilt during the war. Ultimately, both location and communication regarding the Valley of the Fallen tried to bring the distant past to the present, while the recent past becomes distant, serving to establish the narrative of the regime.

Figure 2. View of the cross at El Valle de los Caídos, Madrid, from a distance. October 2018.

3.2. *The reforestation project as a natural legitimization of the regime.*

The Valley of the Fallen is not the only attempt to create a monument in Madrid to commemorate events that occurred during the Civil War. Other examples are the “Junta de Moncloa” by Manuel Herrero Palacios, the “Arch of Triumph” by Modesto López Otero and Pascual Bravo Sanfeliú, or the interesting project “Architectural Dream for a National Exaltation” by Luis Moya. These monuments were all located in the urban environment, close to the city centre. Like Mitchell, one might ask “why [does] the construction of these monuments and associated festivities now take place almost exclusively in cities, especially capital cities?” (Mitchell 2003, 456). Perhaps the impact of visitors is exponentially greater in an urban setting, but the Valley of the Fallen is situated in a remote area beside the mountains and raises questions about the reasons for this atypical design strategy.

The area of Cuelgamuros is 1 377 hectares, 13 areas and 28 centiares. Because only 214 hectares of that sprawling site were covered with trees, there was a reforestation intervention – an artificial operation to introduce and create the idyllic naturalistic landscape that we find there today. More than two million trees were planted as part of the monument (Méndez 1982) to create a “perennial place of pilgrimage in which the greatness of nature puts a worthy framework to the field where the heroes and martyrs of the Crusade rest” (Decreto 1940).

From the beginning, Franco wanted the monument to be located in nature, and constructed nature itself becomes a tool to reinforce the narrative. The monument was never imagined as urban architecture, but a architecture in a naturalistic setting in which the reforestation project serves “as a worthy framework of the work that is built there” (Decreto 1941). It is a transcendent call to power supported by god and nature in the mountains, “a retired place where the grandiose temple of our dead is erected in which to pray for the ages of those who fell in the way of God and of the Fatherland” (Decreto

1940). If “the city is time made visible” (Tuan, 1978), then natural time is the representation of being out of time, and reinforces the idea of eternity with which its promoters to legitimize the regime, as if Franco’s power had sprung forth from nature and was confirmed by religion.

Most of the design consisted of reconstructing the old pine forest to recreate a dream place, a place where nature, religion, and architecture laid the foundations of the new nation. The species for the reforestation were sent from all regions of Spain, so as to create a palimpsest that accumulates all the geographies of the nation (Méndez 1982, 272). In a sense, the reforestation project was also a rhetorical tool to introduce the spaces and times of all regions of Spain and enhance the message of the Valley as a miniature of the state.

Furthermore, the architectonic elements are used to reinforce the idea of a natural instauration of Franco’s power legitimized by religion. Apart from the forest itself, the only element visible from a certain distance is the huge cross, which was carefully integrated in the landscape, as if emerging from nature and colonizing the surrounding area (Méndez 1982, 15). The enormous effort put into the landscape design goes on to demonstrate the importance of using the time of nature to reinforce the narrative of those who built it. In fact, the design of the base of the cross was intended “to ensure that it was not an element imposed on the whole landscape, but added to it and in almost perfect union with the violent and hard cliff” (Méndez 1982, 173). The cross would thus seem to be emerging from the bowels of the mountain naturally to mark the resting place not of the thousands of dead corpses of soldiers and innocents, but especially the bodies of Franco and Primo de Rivera, whose tombs are in perfect symmetry with its axis.

Figure 3. View of the cross at El Valle de los Caídos, which appears to emerge as part of the surrounding landscape, Madrid. October 2018.

4. Religious dimension: The use of time as eternity

4.1. *The basilica to keep time frozen*

There is a huge basilica in the Valley of the Fallen that has been carved out of the mountain and competes in size with St. Peter's in the Vatican (Sueiro 2006; Smith 2007). The architect called the basilica the heart of the architectural compound (Méndez 1982, 73), and its importance in the monument is clear in terms of materiality, as the size of the dome was augmented multiple times – more importantly however, it is clear in the symbolism of its form and function. By introducing the basilica as part of the design strategy, the creators sought to link the narrative of a human event with the eternal time of religion. In a sense, the introduction of the basilica attempts to freeze time and thus fix the event of the crusade permanently in history "not merely evoking the event through "memory" in chronos, but [...] in Kairos, actually participating in the event itself." (Rowe 1999, 19-20).

Religious architecture has been defined as a materialization of kairotic time in which "the idea of the spatial Kairos is to capture and sustain the force of this revelatory moment, to keep the sacred perforation open and accessible indefinitely" (Crosby 2013, 136-137). With the basilica, the design strategy of the Valley of the Fallen strengthens its ties with the eternal time of religion and presents its narrative as something out of the ordinary, as a revelatory moment. Here, religion serves the purpose of dissolving the traces of war, elevating them to the realm of eternity, and creates a narrative capable of sustaining the events as an ever-present legitimization of the regime. The consciousness of linking the timelessness of religion and materiality is clear and transforms the Valley into more than "just a simple material construction, but also a place of prayer and study where, at the same time there are suffrages offered for the souls of those who gave their lives for their Faith and for their Homeland" (Decreto-Ley 1957). As a place of prayer, the monument distinguishes itself from the objective events of the Civil War and creates an atmosphere of immortality. Ultimately, the basilica functions as the artefact that

eludes the fleetingness of human affairs to try to bring the narrative of its creators to the arena of endlessness.

In addition, Franco's tomb is located in the most prominent spot of the basilica – under its dome – where many visitors come to pay their respect or leave flowers. His corpse is part of the ritual of visiting the Valley of the Fallen and it increases the significance of the architecture by inserting strong affects, ideology, and meanings (Anderson 1991; Crampton 2001). This may explain the basilica's peculiar military paraphernalia and surveillance aesthetic. In a sense, the religious dimension is framed in a space where architecture and sculpture come together to create an environment of permanent vigilance in which the "solid masses of granite give the impression of being vigilant turrets of the entrance" (Méndez 1982, 51), or the large number of sculptures in the form of soldiers and archangels armed and permanently poised in threat (Méndez 1982, 91). It is a space where architecture and art try to impart the idea of being under constant watch for future Spaniards, "to serve as an example to future generations" (Decreto-Ley 1957). Ultimately, the basilica and the military representations work together to lend the monument a new temporal dimension, that of eternity, in which the legitimization of the regime through its "crusade" is not a matter of the past, but meant to be permanently present, keeping the event frozen forever.

Figure 4. Interior view of the dome's basilica at El Valle de los Caídos, displaying one of the few examples of military paraphernalia represented inside religious architecture – tank and soldiers. Madrid, October 2018.

4.2. The rituals to keep architecture alive

Paul Valéry gave architecture, above other arts, the maximum potential to bring humans from wild nature to social order (Valéry 1989), not only by setting a spatial order over nature but also by stablishing highly regulated rituals that introduce controlled timing within those spaces. In that sense, the creation of the space of the

basilica comes with the mandatory activation of the architecture through a minimum number of religious rituals (John XXIII 1961). As if it were a living organ, the rituals act as the blood that keep architecture alive. “It must be a latent, living monument, so that when the memory of the current event diffuses in the nebula of time, it would not be necessary to go to the Valley with a book” (Méndez 1982, 12). The Valley of the Fallen had to always breathe, it had to have life in its day-to-day through the work of the monastery, and in eternity through the religious rituality.

The obligations of the abbey include “to maintain the cult with all the splendor that the Church recommends, with special burdens for certain days”, to direct a choir school and the social studies centre, as well as to celebrate spiritual exercises for visitors and workers and take care of the guest house; i.e., to keep the architectural complex alive through rituals, academia and business (Decreto-Ley 1957, art. 5). The temporal approach of the monument is not independent from the visitors, whose role is crucial for infusing life into the architecture. Monks have to perform rituals on certain days that organize how historical memories are lived (Halbwachs 1992; Olick and Robbins 1998; Zerubavel 2004) and coincide with the most important anniversaries of Franco’s regime: the military uprising; Primo de Rivera and Franco’s deaths; the Civil War victory; or the Day of the Caudillo (Aguilar-Fernández and Humlebæk 2002). As the Decree of 1957 points out, to realise its complete function, the monument has to be visited and the Valley of the Fallen has to become a space of pilgrimage that sustains the site's materialization both materially and ideologically (Winter 2010; Autry 2012). The seduction of the monument is always played across time by both the static – buildings and landscape – and the mobile – events, rituals – (Huysen 2003) in which the ritual needs a site to happen, and the site needs some movement to be kept alive. “The monumental cross would not preside over a cold and inert mausoleum. Under its

shadow, next to the dead of Spain, the monastic psalmody and the secular hymns of the Christian liturgy would give life and breath to its stones” (Méndez 1982, 245).

Figure 5. Interior view of the carved basilica at El Valle de los Caídos, Madrid, October 2018.

4.3. *The burial site to keep the time of the dead*

“Stand proud on one of the peaks of the Sierra de Guadarrama, not far from the town of Madrid, the sign of the redeeming cross, as a milestone to heaven, the pre-eminent goal of the journey of earthly life, and at the same time spread its pious arms as protective wings, under which the dead enjoy eternal rest” (John XXIII 1961). The underground basilica is surrounded by crypts in which lay thousands of unidentified corpses from the Civil War. In the final phase of construction, between the 17th March 1959 and 3rd June 1983, when the National Patrimony Institution ordered the process to be stopped (Olmeda 2009; Solé-Barjau 2009; Sueiro 1976), dead bodies arrived at the Valley of the Fallen. According to Abad Anselmo Álvarez, there are 33 847 people buried in the crypts, all of them deceased during the war, but more realistic counts place the figure between 40 000 and 70 000 people (Calleja 2009; Solé-Barjau 2009).

These corpses comprise the largest cemetery of the Spanish Civil War, and the bodies buried in the crypts “were and continue being a crucial constitutive element of the monument” (Ferrándiz 2011, 493). The temporality of the dead bodies is part of the architecture and the material with which the monument has been built (Box, 2010). As the rest of the elements in the Valley of the Fallen, the bodies were a conscious part of the temporal design to infuse immortality into the regime’s narrative: “it was not about projecting a gigantic cemetery for the dead of Spain. It was intended that this Christian rest was also the tribute to a whole nation” (Méndez 1982, 11). Corpses were used as a rhetorical element to provide the monumentality of the architecture with the temporality of death, its eternity.

Interestingly, this was also the first attempt to challenge the integrity of the monument where, in October 2008, the judge Pedraz first authorized the exhumation of the Valley’s crypt 198. This decision follows the process in which dead bodies have been one of the primary channels for dealing with the memory of the Civil War in

recent decades as “exhumations have fostered new strategies of remembrance and mourning” (González-Ruibal 2014, 10).

In the Valley of the Fallen, the eternalness of the dead bodies has prompted questioning of the eternal nature of the monument itself. Republican bodies are anonymous while National corpses are, of course, known and represented. In a sense, the Valley is the “architecture of organized forgetting” (Arif Sargin 2004, 660) in which certain memories are preserved, certain narratives are represented in the stone, and others are completely evaporated (González-Ruibal 2009, 2014), even the names: “because a name means continuity with the past and people without a past are people without a name” (Kundera 1994, 157). It is surprising that the only proposal of the expert report to physically intervene in the architecture (Ministerio de la Presidencia 2011) of the Valley of the Fallen was the same one that was raised during its construction: inscribe the names of those buried in the basilica. A nameless body, then, is simply a corpse that forms part of the rhetoric of architecture and its structure, becoming a “pedagogy of blood” that help to maintain the regime of fear in the public body (Rodrigo 2008). Interestingly enough, the creators of the Valley were extremely conscious about using religion, rituals and death to increase the temporal impact of the monument, but at the same time, these features were the first reasons to question the integrity of the design.

5. Material dimension: The use of time as permanence

5.1. *Architecture to connect with the past*

During and after the Civil War, architects searched for a formula for a “national architecture” that would be capable of symbolizing and enforcing the “new order” against the Republican one, as well as able to express the values and ideology of the new regime. Pedro Muguruza, the General Director of Architecture and first architect of

the Valley of the Fallen, used the reference of Herrera and Villanueva to exalt the antique, the academicism, the rural or the historicist language to “justify the sublimation of both the existence of a struggle that devastated the country and the radical modification of political and social structures” (González-Capitel 1977, 2). The “herrerian” style is based on the architecture of El Escorial and is framed as a purely Spanish mode that was consciously referenced as the intellectual reference for a national architecture (Alonso-del Val 1989). The style served to link the actual regime with the history of royal kings, the Catholic tradition, and the splendid era of the empire (Portela-Sandoval 2002), and to present architects as the only professionals able to make that relation.

The most important attempt to reach that goal was to found the General Directorate of Architecture in order to dominate the production of all the regime’s architecture through the creation of the National Body of Architects. The regime considered architecture a tool for transmitting the ideology of the “new order” and its naturalization over time (González 2016). Somehow, “memory is bound up with matter” (Pearson 2005, 1113) and material aesthetics could therefore also be formed to capture certain memories, as architecture has the capacity to become a small-scale model of a larger order (Barshack 2011). In that sense, the Valley of the Fallen is highly revelatory, as it consciously represents a model for the entire nation, a miniature of what it is supposed to be: religious, rural, archaic, sombre.

The aesthetic choice was examined intensely, with several competitions being held for the design of the Valley of the Fallen. Furthermore, Franco himself sent a proposal for the cross to the competition and visited the construction site several times (Méndez, 1982), demonstrating the importance of the stylistic choices. The Valley represents an incarnation of political and ideological values and its ulterior meaning

(Norberg-Schulz 1979; Relph 1976; Sudjic 2005) through the use of aesthetic tools. In a sense, it is aspiring to become a text carved into stone (Lefebvre 1991), raising the question: is it possible to transform the ideological temporality of such a bold architecture? Is it possible to disconnect the tempo of the Valley of the Fallen with that of royalty or the empire?

With regard to style at any rate, the materiality of the Valley of the Fallen is clearly anchored in Spain's history and royalty, that is to say, to the ancient past. The creators looked to the Monastery of El Escorial – as the most important architectural representation of the Empire – to draw a clear analogy between “the meaning of both monuments and their colossal dimensions” (Méndez 1982, 285). Materiality connects directly with narrative and the meaning of the story that is being told, trying to gather distant time within its stones: “fascist architecture seeks to precipitate the simultaneous presence of all generations in an everlasting present” (Barshack 2011, 240) that tries to be as rigid and immutable as possible. In this sense, all debates surrounding the future of the Valley of the Fallen ultimately face the same conflict: should it be maintained as a heritage site with the preservation that comes with it or committed to a material transformation capable to resignify it? Most of the agents in the process advocate for total conservation (right-wing politicians, the Church or many members of society) – or simple interventions in its materiality (left-wing politicians, the National Heritage Institution, associations of victims or the commission of experts set up by the left-wing government). Interestingly enough, only artists such as Francesc Torres or Fernando Sánchez Castillo have been able to question the integrity of the monument, but have still disregarded the complexity of the material decisions and temporal strategies used by the Valley's creators to produce an architecture designed to remain connected with the monument's own artificial past.

Figure 4. Esplanade in front of the basilica at El Valle de los Caídos, Madrid, October 2018.

5.2. *Architecture to affect space and time as scenography*

Totalitarian architecture has often been defined as scenographic (Frampton 2007) because it builds the environment as a narrative rather than a function. In the context of Francoist architecture, the professor González-Capitel defined the approach of that period, and especially the work of Pedro Muguruza, as being far from rationality and closer to theatrical features: “invented problems, empty themes, were resolved through a scenographic understanding” (González-Capitel 1977, 3). This strategy is corroborated by the architect of the Valley of the Fallen himself: “my intention was clearly to prepare the visitor's spirit to the impression that this perspective will cause in him” (Méndez 1982, 91). The main goal of the project was to construct an experience rather than solve a certain problem; the architecture was meant to be visited, admired, and affective.

It is important to note that within scenographic architecture, power “works through the ambient qualities of the space, where the experience of it is itself the expression of power” (Allen 2006, 441). In the case of the Valley of the Fallen, even finishing materials serve the purpose of creating an affective atmosphere: “the dark pavement of marble and granite, perfectly polished, offers a thousand contrasts, and on it, the small silhouettes of those who cross it, seem to slide” (Méndez 1982, 98). In this context, materiality transforms passers-by into ghosts or zombies, whose experience is amplified by actually walking along an inhuman architecture whilst surrounded by dead bodies. Violence and monumentality are inextricably related, with both infusing each other to evoke strong feelings of rejection or fascination through materiality (Ashworth 2008). The Valley of the Fallen is not only a representation or image of the regime, but also a pilgrimage site that aspires to lead an affective trace on every visitor who leaves the complex. Here, architecture uses time to extend the capacity of the Valley to

conquer quotidian time and to reinforce Franco's narrative outside the spatial boundaries of the monument.

In that sense, the extension of the experience of the Valley is not constrained to the delimitations of Cuelgamuros. Through the size of the cross that is seen from many kilometres away, it is also an artefact that looks for contemplation from all directions (Mendez 1982, 173). The size and form of the cross are used as a means of communication and extend the ideological reach of the Valley to a larger territory. The Valley's architecture is more related to notions of seduction (Dovey 2008; Allen 2006) in which grandiosity, personalism and world records aspire to freeze a moment of time in the minds of its visitors by designing an scenographic project that can make a mark on everyone. Its goal is to have an impact on the viewer, to create an affective response (Anderson 2006; McCormack 2003; Thrift 2004; Amin and Thrift 2002) as a tangible reminder, a material message meant to affect the visitors through its architecture and extend the timing of the events to all of society (Méndez 1982, 11).

5.3. *Architecture to last*

"If all records told the same tale – then the lie passed into history and became truth. 'Who controls the past,' ran the Party slogan, 'controls the future: who controls the present controls the past'" (Orwell 1980, 56). Time as past, present, or future has the power to be transformed, manipulated, and directly constructed by those in a dominant position to send the desired message. The long-term vision of the promoters of the Valley of the Fallen was clear, and durability was desired and designed so the message could be highly permanent.

Everlastingness is a common feature of monumentality; "the most beautiful monuments are imposing in their durability. A cyclopean wall achieves monumental beauty because it seems eternal, because it seems to have escaped time" (Lefebvre

1991, 221). This aim is clear from the point of view of the architect of the Valley who often uses mythological language to describe the monument (Méndez 1982, 239). Despite the symbolic language, the reality is that the monument was imagined and designed for the future; future time was part of the design equation, and materiality was applied accordingly. The idea of permanence over centuries was so clear that the structure of the cross was calculated “not for a term of one hundred years, as is general, but for a thousand years” (Méndez 1982, 179).

Material decisions were made to outlast the current status quo and become something else. Professor Dovey also detects this peculiar temporal feature in Nazi architecture: “Hitler was also much influenced by Rome. He wanted buildings that would outlast the Reich, believing that architecture had inspirational inertia which could carry a national spirit through periods of decline, and retain its meaning in decay. This was what Speer termed the ‘theory of ruin value’” (Dovey 2008, 57). In this context, the Valley’s location in nature is linked to the romantic view of Piranesi’s natural ruins, where the architecture of the Valley of the Fallen consciously seeks to create a fictional landscape far from the quotidian, the urban, and more related to immortality, everlastingness and perpetuity. Materiality in the Valley is seen as a durable tool that can extend the message of the regime across generations with special importance to generating an affective response rather than a rational one.

6. The Valley of the Fallen as a time accumulator

6.1. The complex as a whole: Nature, religion and materiality

“The National Monument of the Valley of the Fallen means a work of enormous transcendence and representativeness that deserves the general attention of all Spaniards and therefore, the particular of the Government of the Nation” (Decreto 1967, 955). The

importance and interest of each tactic and piece spread around the Valley has great individual value, but it is the relation between all of them what makes the whole complex, in the words of Pope John XXIII, "unique" (John XXIII 1961). The size of the monument and its fragmented nature formed by distant and independent pieces make the visit to the monument a temporal experience, a tour between different architectures that together form the Valley of the Fallen; as Deleuze explains: "time is not the interior in us, but just the opposite, the interiority in which we are, in which we move, live and change..." (Deleuze 1989 NEED THE PAGE FOR A DIRECT QUOTE). Here, temporal elements regarding architecture co-exist in one place and at the same time – the basilica, forest, monastery or academy – both in the present and with all its pasts (Osborne 1995), which come together to conform a total architecture meant to dominate time.

"When I am walking, the evenness or unevenness of the ground upon which I walk affects how I take my next step" (Rodemeyer 2015, 131). In this sense, the way the Valley of the Fallen uses spatial and aesthetic features to condition or influence the time of the visitor is completely conscious, creating an open path that tries to lead to the same story. Successful or not, the display is designed to affect the experience of the visitor with all of its iconic items from entrance to exit. Architecture in this sense is meant to create a theatrical tour rather than a singular event and affect the temporalization of the individual body, to reach to every person "through an integrated, embodied consciousness" (Rodemeyer 2015, 132) that uses materiality as a rhetorical tool to establish meaning.

Rhetoric is intimately related to architecture, infusing it to increase its affective potential and legitimization both in theory and practice (Goodnight 2013; Bertazzo 2008; McKeon 1987). Somehow, all architectural rhetoric in the Valley of the Fallen is

meant to create a moment out of time with a clear entrance that starts with an immersion in an idyllic forest and continues by visiting a basilica that is carved from the mountain, on top of which stands a huge cross, aligned with the dead bodies of Francisco Franco and Primo de Rivera and surrounded by thousands of corpses. The whole tour was designed so architecture could be absorbed in the body of every visitor and legitimize Franco's regime. The pretension was to transform history into reality and bring it to a continuous present. Of course, that artificial and pretended present is disrupted nowadays (Casqueiro 2019; Madina 2018), making the Valley of the Fallen a site of conflictive heritage (Burström and Gelderblom 2011) whose materiality is still unchangeable for economic and social reasons (El País 2018). Debates revolve around the ideological need to resignify the monument and the economic effort to do so. In that sense, the promoters of the monument were successful in generating an intricate artefact whose material and symbolic relations make the resignification a complex process in which soft and partial interventions appear unviable. Perhaps the complexity of the design strategies strengthen the immobility of the Valley of the Fallen.

6.2. *The complex as heritage: The not-so-frozen time*

“Time temporalizes, is temporalized” (Grant, McNeilly, and Veerapen 2015, 3). The difficulty of working with time as a design tool is its changeable inner nature; it cannot be programmed: time is invoked; time is designed but simultaneously passes and changes. The Valley of the Fallen is a great example because of the explicit and conscious utilization of time in its design that, nowadays, has been shown to have failed in part, though not in regards to its material integrity: If we were to travel there today, we would see the same Valley of the Fallen as designed by Diego Mendez.

The current temporal dissonance of the Valley of the Fallen, in which the narrative is no longer sustainable, but the architecture remains the same, follows a logic

in which monuments, as complex artefacts, are pierced by a multiplicity of agents and social bodies (Taylor 2015; Márquez & Rozas-Krause 2016). In the case of the Valley, from the inauguration of the monument, Franco appointed National Patrimony as the agent in charge of the complex, an operation that automatically gave the monument heritage status: it is static, immutable and indisputable. Furthermore, by appointing the Benedictine monks as the Valley's inhabitants and constructing a basilica, religion and canonical law united with heritage legislation to extend indefinite protection over the materialization. Between both institutions, the legal assemblage is very difficult to disentangle, as heritage directly transforms an architecture into history that should be preserved without modifications. The innate value of heritage, promoted by National Patrimony, brings the idea of a hygienic architecture whose artistic relevance is beyond all other considerations. This static view of architecture disregards important aspects of materiality itself such as ideology, culture or legitimacy (Smith 2006) and tries to impede its evolution over time, bringing to the present objects that generate multidirectional conflicts. "Things that were once considered normal or even salutary, fall into disrepute and end up being thought of as simply not done" (Neumann 2018, 351).

In the case of the Valley, a media war broke out when the judge Baltasar Garzón started to investigate Francoist crimes in 2008 (Garzón 2008), bringing the temporal and spatial conflicts of the monument to the public realm with dozens of covers in the newspapers, and with even the opposition retransmitting the religious ceremonies held in the basilica on television, by viewer demand. While the debate about Franco's regime was stimulated, the materiality of the Valley itself has not been modified. Those who defend preservation of the Valley of the Fallen have always tried to situate the conflict in the heritage debate and create distance from its political context (Fuentes-Vega 2017)

by trying to place the monument above time. Its artistic value and its status as heritage locate it in a different time – in the time of history, where humans cannot judge it, because its artistic and architectural values are above the temporality of political values.

Even when the government appointed an expert commission to examine the future of the Valley, their final report stated that “this construction stores suffering and blood. Therefore, and even if only for that, it is maximally respectable and must be maintained. The itinerary suffered by those who built it and the memory of those buried there should not be erased” (Ministerio de la Presidencia 2011, 7). Although the invisibility of the victims of the Civil War has begun to be denaturalized (Otero 2018), the materiality of the monument is still difficult to challenge, as not even the Historical Memory Law forbids removing Francoist symbols because of their artistic value (Ley 2007, 52).

Somehow, there is still a lack of critical reflection of the relation of architecture and time by accepting the static, the immutable features of space, instead of considering the Valley of the Fallen as a moving architecture that needs to change in order to remain sustainable in a democratic society. Regarding its current legal regime, the Valley would probably remain physically identical and be “transformed gradually in a monument to drift, so completely unrelated to contemporary Spanish society as to the eternity sought” (Ferrándiz 2011, 499).

7. Conclusion

The promoters of the Valley of the Fallen designed an architecture that tries to dominate time and accumulate temporality as its most important design tool. This strategy brings architecture to the front line of dominance in which the only goal of its materiality is to use the time of the dead, the time of religion, the time of nature and the time of history to create a narrative able to legitimize Franco’s regime and become a

micro-cosmos of the whole nation's collective imaginary. The Valley of the Fallen tries to close the future, bring the past to the present and, thereby extend the present eternally (Hobbes 1962) through the use of materiality, symbolism and rituals; it is an architecture to command time. Still, the capacity of the Valley of the Fallen to achieve this goal and extend its power to the quotidian environments of Spanish society is doubtful; these are more the aspirations of those responsible for its building (Stefanovic 1994; Bell et al. 1990; Sudjic, 2005) than the reality of its outcome. In the end, "time is endowed with the possibilities of the unexpected, the possibilities of change" (Sennett 1990, 115) and demonstrated by the current debates and conflicts. In this sense, the Valley is a progressive architecture whose meaning and significance evolve according to its context, whilst its materiality remains unchanged. This represents a crucial conflict that could be extrapolated to other conflictive architectures around the world: can monuments be resignified without intervention in their material formalization? In the case of the Valley, this represents an almost impossible task because of the strong and conscious design of architecture by its creators to represent one single narrative across time.

The different elements present in the Valley of the Fallen, such as the basilica carved out of the mountain, the gigantic cross, the monastery or the non-urban landscape, must be understood in the entirety of the relation and movement between them. The architectural design constructs a complete experience of the extraordinary throughout the whole complex where time is stopped and frozen in a kairotic moment – the crusade – to legitimize a certain organization and distribution of power. Actually, the size, distance and fragmentation of the different parts of the Valley allow the visitor to be lost, to wander around the whole complex. In this sense, the use of time visiting the Valley is not designed as something standardized or tabulated, increasing the

complexity and duration of the visit. There is even the possibility to spend the night in the Valley's guest house, which reinforces the idea of the monument as a territory rather than a building. In this sense, being in the mountains and far away from the urban environment only potentiates this situation. Throughout the article, the importance and conscious design of time becomes apparent, constructing an artefact capable of affecting both the present and the past of Spanish society.

This temporal intention was so bold that even the use of corpses served to unite religion, nature, and death. "Once each of those [crypts] were filled, their accesses were finally closed with stone, thus being incorporated into the mountain" (Méndez 1982, 137). So, when the corpses started to melt together with the structure of the basilica and the rocks of the mountain in the humidity, it was only a representation of an extravagant feature of the whole idea to dominate time from death, religion, nature, and monumentality.

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